

Leader-Member Exchange Relationship, School Culture, And Job Satisfaction: Their Implication to Senior High School Teachers' Work Performance

Aga Emm D. Mahinay

Liceo de Cagayan University, Cagayan de Oro City, Misamis Oriental, Philippines

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Abstract:

Teaching might not be the most popular profession in the world, but it is undoubtedly the most populated. With the change in the Department of Education in the Philippines, school leaders and teachers are challenged to maintain work performance under stressful conditions. The aim of this study is to investigate the implication of leader-member exchange relationship, school culture, job satisfaction on teachers' work performance. This study utilized descriptive correlational design and stratified random sampling on the selection of the 157 senior high school teachers from two private universities in Cagayan de Oro City, Academic Year 2023-2024. Data revealed that teachers and principals have a very strong leader-

member exchange relationship and shows no significant difference on their relationship. Teachers' meets their expectations in their overall school culture, has an overall moderate job satisfaction, and exhibits strength on their overall work performance. The study also reveals no significant difference of the teachers' overall work performance in terms of profile. However, contribution on LMX, teachers' collaboration on school culture, and job responsibilities and community attachments/linkages have contributed teachers' work performance. Thus, the theory of Maslow confirms teachers' needs based on the study's results. Therefore, this study recommends teachers to possibly show sense of openness to their principal, foster collaboration with colleagues, enroll in graduates studies, engage in community services and teachers serving 5 years above to possibly improve their personal attributes and engagement in community activities. Principals, on the other hand, to provide equal opportunities and minimize the work of the teachers. School administrators to possibly meet the needs of the teaching staff in improving job satisfaction and future research to consider other variables as part of the study's limitations.

Keywords: *leader-member exchange relationship, school culture, job satisfaction, teachers' work performance.*

Introduction

Teaching may not be the most popular profession in the world, it is undoubtedly the most populated. There are 57 million teachers in the world, approximately two-thirds of whom work in the developing world. Teachers play a vital role in each country's educational system

and are regarded as valued assets (Ambotang and Hamid, 2021).

The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, or R.A. 10533, caused a hornet nest to appear, mostly among senior high school teachers. The basic education curriculum of the Philippines changed when the Enhanced Basic Education

Act of 2013, also known as the Republic Act 10533, came into effect.

Over the years, teachers and the teaching profession in the Philippines have been confronted with various issues and concerns that directly or indirectly affect them.

Decano and Vallejo (2019) mentioned that private secondary school teachers have lower teaching performance than public secondary teachers. This was supported by Magulod (2017), who stated that in terms of the level of school performance in basic education, public schools perform better than private schools.

Parents prefer private schools with the expectation of better education. The characteristics and qualifications of teachers in private schools are cited as the reasons for this demand. Private schools, which must meet these demands, want their teachers to perform well and provide high-quality education (Turkoglu and Aypay, 2022).

As mentioned by Selamat, Taufiq & Kamalu (2013), a teacher's work performance is important for ensuring the quality of instruction at school. Therefore, there is a need to increase the importance of identifying factors that influence teachers' work performance.

Many related studies have shown that various factors influence teachers' workplace performance. However, the present study focuses on teachers' profiles, leader-member exchange relationships, school culture, and job satisfaction.

Objective

The main objectives of this study were to: (1) determine participants' profiles in terms of age, sex, marital status, and length of service; (2) seek the participants' leader-member exchange relationship, school culture, job satisfaction, and work performance level; (3) describe the participant's level of relationship and difference to their principal; and (4) determine which underlying factors significantly contribute to teachers' work performance.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

Leader - Member Exchange Relationship and LMX Theory

The leader-member exchange (LMX) theory was proposed by Graen and Uhl-Bien in 1995. This theory is a relationship-based approach to leadership that focuses on the two-way (dyadic) relationship between leaders and followers. This suggests that leaders and followers develop unique relationships based on their social exchanges, and the quality of these exchanges within an organization can influence employee outcomes.

Stepanek and Paul (2022) mentioned that LMX is most often measured using the leader-member exchange 7 questionnaire (LMX-7), a seven-item scale that considers LMX to be a unidimensional construct. However, LMX can also be measured via the LMX-MDM, which was introduced by Liden and Maslyn (1998) and considers LMX to four dimensions: affective, loyalty, contribution, and professionalism. Both LMX-7 and LMX-MDM can be adapted to collect ratings from the leader and members by conversely changing the items to reflect a leader's relationship with their subordinates.

However, this study will use the LMX-MDM, which uses a dyadic multidimensionality and will only consider the indicators applicable to the study, including affective, contribution, and professionalism in promoting teachers' work performance.

School Culture and The Dimensions of School Culture

School culture is the social indoctrination of unwritten rules that employees learn as they try to fit into a group or organization (Gruenert & Whitaker, 2015). Considering that the culture of a school is a powerful influence on members' behavior, a clear understanding of the culture of a school is, without a doubt, vital for its improvement.

Additionally, school culture emanates from interpersonal interactions between individual teachers and groups of teachers and their common perceptions and shared meanings that

reflect collective beliefs, attitudes, and values (Gun et. al., 2013).

This study adapted the School Culture Survey of Gruent and Valentine (1998), considering indicators that are applicable in the context of teachers' work performance, including collaborative leadership, teacher collaboration, professional development, unity of purpose, and collegial support, excluding learning partnerships.

The dimensions of school culture proposed by Muhammad (2009) explores various aspects and components of school culture and their impact on overall school effectiveness. These dimensions include: Collaborative Culture, Collegial Culture, Learning Culture and, The result-oriented Culture.

However, it has been said that the dimensions of culture within a school environment have a significant impact on teachers' workplace

performance. The Collaborative and Collegial Culture dimensions.

Based on the indicators of the School Culture Survey (Gruent and Valentine,1998) and the Dimensions of School Culture Framework (Muhammad, 2008), it can be inferred that the following indicators of school culture surveys are reflective of both collaborative and collegial culture under the Dimensions of School Culture Framework.

Job Satisfaction and Herzberg's Motivator-Hygiene Theory

Job satisfaction refers to the attitudes and feelings people have about their work. Positive and favorable attitudes towards the job indicate job satisfaction. Negative and unfavorable attitudes towards a job indicate job dissatisfaction (Armstrong, 2006; Aziri, 2011).

Figure 1. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory of Motivation

According to Aziri (2011), job satisfaction is one of the most complex areas facing managers today when it comes to managing employees. Many studies have demonstrated an unusually large impact of job satisfaction on the motivation of workers, while the level of motivation has an impact on productivity, and hence, on performance.

Herzberg's Theory of Job Satisfaction (1959) or better dubbed as a theory of motivation is also known as Herzberg's Two Factor Theory. Nickerson (2023) argues that there are separate sets of mutually exclusive factors in the

workplace that cause either job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. According to Herzberg, motivators ensure job satisfaction, while a lack of hygiene factors spawns job dissatisfaction. Herzberg further explained that an employee needs to meet the motivating factors like performance and achievement, recognition, job status, responsibility, opportunities for advancement, personal growth, and the work itself to increase job satisfaction. However, the absence of "hygiene" factors like salary, working conditions, physical workspace, job security, job status, relationship with supervisors, quality of

supervisors, and policies and rules the employee will increase their dissatisfaction with their job. If an employer wants to motivate the team to perform better in the company, it is necessary to focus on factors that lead to satisfaction.

Additionally, Kuijk (2018) illustrated two-factor theory in practice. Accordingly, teachers with high hygiene and low motivation factors had fewer complaints but were not motivated.

Conversely, teachers with low hygiene and high motivation factors are motivated to work but have complaints. On the other hand, teachers with high hygiene and motivation factors show an ideal situation in which they have no complaints and are highly motivated. However, teachers with low hygiene and low motivation represent the worst situation, in which teachers are not motivated and have complaints.

Figure 2. Two-Factor Theory in Practice

He added that school organizations and managers want their teams to have the best possible performance. Motivating teachers really works when things bother them or the things they complain about disappear. Thus, to motivate teachers using motivation factors, hygiene factors need to be considered first.

Two-factor motivation theory has since become one of the most commonly used theoretical frameworks in job satisfaction research (Dion, 2006; Nickerson, 2023).

Teachers' Work Performance

Teacher work performance is defined as the duties performed by a teacher during a particular period in the school system to achieve organizational goals (Kumari and Kumar, 2023). Teachers play a fundamental and dynamic role in the educational system. Thus, a teacher's work performance is important to ensure the quality of instruction at school. According to Haryaka and Sjamsir (2021), the quality of education in

schools is largely determined by teachers' performance in the learning process.

In this study, the antecedents used in measuring teachers' work performance was adopted from the teachers' work performance evaluation used in the university. These includes: personal attributes, professionalism, instructional planning and delivery, work environment, and community service.

Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Need is the overarching theory of this study. Abraham Maslow's theory in 1943 shows the level of human needs sought to fulfill, which motivates one's behavior. According to Maslow (1943, 1954), human needs are arranged in a hierarchy, with physiological (survival) needs at the bottom and the more creative and intellectually oriented 'self-actualization' needs at the top. Maslow argues that survival needs must be satisfied before an individual can satisfy higher needs.

Figure 3. Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

According to Kurt (2020), this theory can be applied in the field of education to help school organizations understand the different needs of teachers and how to meet them. For the school to have a strong foundation, it must learn how to understand these needs and create a more supportive environment among teachers. In addition, this theory is based on the idea that schools must satisfy teachers' needs to reach their full potential. The theory divides teachers' needs into five categories: physiological, safety, love and social belonging, esteem, and self-actualization.

With this theory, the researcher believed that if the teacher's need will be satisfied in terms of their leader-member exchange relationship, school culture, job satisfaction, and work performance level, their work performance will be in success.

Materials and Methods

This study used a descriptive, correlational research design. A descriptive correlational design is used in research studies that aim to establish the relationship between different variables (McBurney & White, 2009; Panda, 2023). Based on the nature of the study, it sought to determine the relationships of work performance to leader-member exchange relationships, school culture, and job satisfaction.

Thus, the study was conducted in two private universities in Cagayan de Oro City, Misamis Oriental, Academic Year 2023-2024. University A is a private Catholic university grounded in the Ignatian tradition, while University B is a prime private, non-sectarian university.

Additionally, this research was carried out on 157 senior high school participants teaching different strands (ABM, HUMSS, STEM, and TECH-VOC).

During the selection of the participants, Cochran Test and stratified random sampling was utilized to get the desired participants.

It is worth noting that before the data gathering, the researcher ensures the validity and reliability of the questionnaire where the tool underwent face and content validity from the experts of the field as well as the reliability testing such as the use of classical test theory to get the desired acceptable Cronbach's Alpha. Furthermore, the letter of consent was also given to the schools as well as to the participants for ethical procedures. Thus, this study was implemented under the following ethical considerations for the assurance that this paper has followed proper safeguards and guidelines.

Results

The following results were obtained after analyzing the data:

Majority of the participants are within the age range of 22-26, female, single, and has served in their institution 5 years and below.

Principals claim that teachers have a “Strong Relationship” in Affective, and “Very Strong” in Contribution and Professionalism while teachers perceived principals having a “Very Strong Relationship” in Affection and Professionalism and “Strong” in Contribution. In sum, participants have a “Very Strong Relationship” in their overall Leader-Member Exchange Relationship.

On the other hand, School Culture dimensions such as Collaborative Leadership, Teacher Collaboration, Professional Development, Unity of Purpose, and Collegial Support have the same rating of “Meets Expectations” as well as its overall School Culture rating.

Participants have an overall “Moderately Satisfied” rating in their Job Satisfaction along with its dimensions on; Security, Work Environment, Job Responsibilities, and Community Attachments.

Thus, both Professional Attributes and Learning Environment of teacher’s Work Performance dimension have a rating of “Demonstrates Excellence” while Professionalism, Instructional Planning and Delivery, and Community Service “Exhibits Strength”. Teacher’s work performance has an overall rating of “Exhibits Strength”.

Participants’ age, sex, and civil status has no significant difference in their work performance. However, teacher’s work performance in terms of personal attributes and community service is significant when it comes to their length of service. Overall, participant’s work performance has no significant difference in terms of their profile.

However, the exchange relationship between members and their leaders has significant differences, particularly in the affective domain. However, there is no significant difference in terms of their overall leader-member exchange relationship.

Only the contribution of leader-member exchange relationships has a highly significant

influence on teachers’ work performance. Affective and professionalism had no significant impact on teachers’ work performance.

Collaborative Leadership, Professional Development, Unity of Purpose and Collegial Support on School Culture has no direct impact as Teachers Collaboration best predicts teacher’s Work Performance.

Lastly, Job Responsibilities and Community Attachments/Linkages on Job Satisfaction significantly contributed to teachers’ Work Performance while Security and Work Environment did not contribute to teachers’ Work Performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Considering the demographics of the participants, it can be concluded that the Teacher Induction Program for the Teachers and Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) is helpful because it is a systematic and comprehensive professional development program for beginning teachers with 0–3 years of teaching experience that has been developed to improve teachers’ knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values.

On the other hand, beginner teachers often view each day as an opportunity for growth and learning, as seasoned teachers often handle leadership roles that may contribute to stress and work-life imbalance, affecting their personal attributes and community engagement. In some way, it is an opportunity for the beginner teachers to actualize their full potential, personal growth and their self-worth. As mentioned by Abraham Maslow (1943), teachers are more likely to be motivated and perform at a high level if they are able to self-actualize their full potential and personal growth and fulfill their esteem needs.

In terms of the leader–member exchange relationship, because of the positive exchange of both principals and teachers, they were able to establish a healthy and positive relationship in

the workplace. This supports the claim of the LMX theory where Graen and Uhl-bien (1995) mentioned that the leaders and followers develop a unique relationship based on their social exchanges. It is also highlighted in the Maslow's Hierarchy of Need (1943) in "Love and Belongingness" category that teachers, as social being, have a need for positive relationships and a sense of belongingness. And as seen on the result, it can be concluded that both principals and teachers fulfill that need as positive contribution between leader and members help teachers exhibiting strength in their work performance as both provides help and support with one another.

A comprehensive analysis of school culture indicators reveals a predominantly positive environment within both private schools, creating a more empowered, cohesive, and purpose-driven educational environment. Working collaboratively to one another has a significant influence on participants' work performance. Muhammad (2009) on his school culture framework on collaborative culture dimension, mentioned the importance of collaboration and cooperation among school staff in enhancing teacher work performance. Suggestive to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943), teachers thrive in a supportive and collaborative work environment where they can develop positive relationships that can fulfil their need for belongingness, which is essential for their well-being and work performance.

Participants moderate satisfaction in their jobs might stem from a stable income and job security in the present, but they may still harbor concerns about economic changes, potential fluctuations in the job market, or how external factors could impact their future financial security. Teachers might be contemplating their long-term career trajectory, including concerns about retirement plans, potential succession strategies in the educational institution, and opportunities for newer teachers. In addition, while positive aspects contribute to their contentment, there are also areas that could be improved to enhance job satisfaction. A moderate level of satisfaction may be indicative of a delicate balance between the positive and

negative factors influencing the teaching profession. It is crucial for educational institutions and policymakers to recognize the factors that contribute to teacher satisfaction and discontent, as this understanding can inform targeted interventions and improvements. This study underscores the importance of ongoing efforts to create a supportive and enriching work environment for educators, fostering their professional growth and job satisfaction. These findings highlight the need for continuous dialogue between teachers and administrators to address concerns and implement strategies that can positively impact overall job satisfaction. Ultimately, the pursuit of enhancing teacher satisfaction is paramount for educators' overall well-being and the quality of education they provide to students. As mentioned by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959), motivators ensure job satisfaction, while the lack of hygiene factors increases dissatisfaction. In support of this, Maslow(1943) mentioned that human beings are motivated by goal accomplishment, and that achieving these goals allows humans to meet their individual wants and needs. In summary, satisfying and addressing teachers' needs will help them focus on their professional duties and enhance their workplace performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the researcher presents the following recommendations:

Teachers. That teachers explore the possibility of showing more openness to their principals. Heighten the possibility of collaboration with colleagues, engage in professional development, particularly enrolling in graduate studies, establish unity of purpose, and promote collegial support. To possibly engage in community activities. Teachers serving the institution for more than five years have the possibility of improving the aspect of personal attributes and exerting effort to engage in community activities. Volunteer in community services.

Principal/Assistant Principal. To explore the possibility of heightening collaboration among teachers, consider minimizing additional tasks to avoid heavy workload and stress if not part of the teacher's job description and pay, and possibly provide equal opportunities for teachers and time to engage in community activities.

School Administrators. Possibly provide a clear sense of direction for teachers on their job responsibilities, reconsider the policies particularly on salary and benefits, improve the working condition facilities (heating, lighting, ventilation etc.), and conduciveness of the working conditions.

School Human Resource Department. Possibly give newly hired teachers a sense clarity of the school's mission.

For future researchers. Expand possibly the research setting by considering both private and public institutions as part of the limitation of this study. It is also recommended to explore other variables that were not included in the study.

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